

**This scale diagram, illustrates,
that, our finite air atmosphere, is only a very delicate membrane,
upon the entire surface, of our original perfect beautiful peaceful planet Earth.**

The above reason, is why, our finite air atmosphere, is being adversely affected,
by the distressingly huge annual magnitude, of our world carbon dioxide emissions, which are caused by,
the distressingly huge annual magnitude, of our world population demand for carbon combustion energy.

The inner blue circle: the diameter of our planet earth is 12,742 kilometres.

The 1st red circle: 99% of the mass of our atmosphere is within 32 kilometres of the surface of our Earth.

The 2nd red circle: 99.99997% of the mass of our atmosphere is within 100 kilometres of the surface of our Earth.

Our Brazil COP30 climate conference president André Corrêa do Lago, our IPCC, & all our world's climate scientists,
have the right, to ask us, our whole world population, in all our whole world's news services:

**“Please can we, our whole world population, please really care, and please really choose,
to use, less or much less, carbon combustion energy, every day, now and forevermore, please.”**

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